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Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence and Instructional Support as Predictors of Reading Proficiency among SHS Students

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Abstract

The primary purpose of this study was to examine the influence of verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support on the reading proficiency of SHS students. There is an affirmation that verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support predict reading proficiency. This study employed a quantitative research design, utilizing the descriptive-correlational method. A simple random sampling method was employed to select the research samples, and survey questionnaires were used to collect the data. Likewise, mean and standard deviation, Pearson (r), and regression analysis were the statistical tools utilized to answer the research objectives. Findings revealed that the levels of instructional support and reading proficiency of SHS students are rated very high, while the level of verbal-linguistic intelligence is rated high. Nonetheless, a significant relationship exists between the variables under investigation. Thus, this connects to the idea that verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support are good predictors of reading proficiency. The regression analysis revealed that these two factors collectively account for 47.4% of the variation in reading proficiency, confirming their substantial influence.

Keywords: *verbal-linguistic intelligence, instructional support, reading proficiency, Davao City, Philippines*

Introduction

Reading proficiency is the ability to critically understand, analyze, and engage with the text in addition to decoding it (Compton, 2023). Nevertheless, studies have shown that the reading ability of senior high school students is diminishing. The 2018 results of the Programme for International Student Assessment (PISA) showed that the Philippines had the lowest average reading score of 340, which was below the OECD average (OECD, 2019a). Additionally, national assessments have shown that many senior high school students struggle to comprehend readings adequately. This inability then affects students' abilities to analyze and synthesize various pieces of information (DepEd, 2023). Furthermore, factors such as poor instructional support, a lack of reading materials, and students' verbal-linguistic intelligence (Abdulrahman et al., 2023) have contributed to students' reading ability and proficiency.

Reading ability is crucial not only to the academic achievement of individual students but also to a framework of larger social and economic engagement. Reading develops students' ability to assess knowledge, participate in thoughtful and productive democratic practices, and promote lifelong learning (Graham & Harris, 2021). For SHS students preparing for higher education and employment, strong reading skills are essential for future success in the workforce. The World Bank and UIS (2022) emphasized reading proficiency at the secondary level as an indicator of future productivity and income potential. In addition, education systems also depend on literate individuals to support civic duties, enhance innovation, and improve national competitiveness (OECD, 2019b). Thus, addressing reading proficiency issues is a matter of public urgency that directly affects social development and equity.

Although a substantial body of educational literature exists on reading proficiency, there is limited research that focuses on the interaction between verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support in enhancing reading outcomes among SHS students. Sadeghi et al. (2019) found that verbal-linguistic intelligence is positively associated with reading skills in EFL contexts; however, the study did not explore how this intelligence interacts with the quality of instructional support.

Similarly, Abdulrahman et al. (2023) highlighted the influence of multiple intelligences on reading performance but called for further research on how teachers' instructional practices could complement students' cognitive strengths. The current study seeks to bridge these gaps by examining the combined effects of verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support on the reading proficiency of SHS students.

Research Objectives

The purpose of this study was to determine the influence of verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support on the reading proficiency of SHS students. More explicitly, the study sought to answer the following objectives:

1. To describe the level of verbal-linguistic intelligence of SHS students.
2. To ascertain the level of instructional support of SHS students.
3. To assess the level of the reading proficiency of SHS students.
4. To determine the relationship between:
 - 4.1. verbal-linguistic intelligence and reading proficiency; and
 - 4.2. instructional support and reading proficiency.
5. To test the influence of verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support on the reading proficiency of SHS students.

Literature Review

Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence

Verbal-linguistic intelligence refers to the ability to effectively use language, both spoken and written, to express thoughts, ideas, and emotions. This form of intelligence is characterized by an individual's ability to comprehend, manipulate, and produce language with proficiency. According to Handayani et al. (2021), individuals with high verbal-linguistic intelligence can effectively utilize words for various purposes, including argumentation, persuasion, and instruction. In the framework of Howard Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences, verbal-linguistic intelligence is recognized as an advanced form of verbal ability that is sensitive to the phonological, syntactic, and semantic elements of language (Hasanudin & Fitrianiingsih, 2020). The importance of verbal-linguistic intelligence extends beyond simple language use; it encompasses a profound understanding of how language functions across various contexts and is a crucial skill in both social and academic settings (Mujiono et al., 2023; Garavand et al., 2023). Scholars emphasize that verbal-linguistic intelligence involves both an inherent aptitude for language and an acquired ability to manipulate words effectively to achieve specific goals (Intan et al., 2022).

This intelligence is often displayed when individuals engage in activities such as debating, instructing, storytelling, or negotiating. For instance, Gunawan et al. (2022) highlight how linguistic intelligence enables individuals to structure thoughts clearly and convey their messages through words, whether in written form or verbal expression. This intelligence is not only integral in day-to-day communication but also plays a significant role in academic success, particularly in the areas of reading, writing, and oral expression. Bartolomei-Torres (2020) notes that verbal-linguistic intelligence is considered one of the most universally distributed forms of intelligence, with nearly every person being able to speak and most individuals being capable of reading and writing. Moreover, this intelligence is particularly significant because it is directly linked to the academic achievement of students across various educational disciplines, as the ability to use language effectively is essential for comprehension and expression (Hasanudin & Fitrianiingsih, 2020; Setyaningsih et al., 2022).

Instructional Support

Instructional support encompasses the array of teaching strategies, resources, and interventions provided by educators to enhance students' learning experiences and foster academic success. Pianta et al. (2020) define instructional support as a multifaceted approach that encompasses teacher feedback, scaffolding, differentiated instruction, and the provision of learning materials tailored to the diverse needs of students. As highlighted by Alqurashi (2018), such support is essential for creating a conducive learning environment where students can thrive. Adequate instructional support is essential for student engagement, comprehension, and skill development, particularly in the domain of reading proficiency. Hamre and Downer (2021) emphasize that such support is crucial in helping students overcome learning challenges and excel academically, particularly in language-related tasks, where it promotes a deeper understanding of content and improves the development of critical skills (Escosar & Caloc, 2024).

Instructional support involves both classroom-based and institutional interventions, all designed to improve student learning outcomes (Haw et al., 2021). These interventions may include direct instruction, collaborative learning opportunities, tutoring programs, and the integration of technology-assisted learning tools. In addition, Zhang and Singh (2025) emphasized that instructional scaffolding is instrumental in helping students develop the critical reading strategies needed for comprehension and academic growth. This type of support not only enhances students' understanding of content but also facilitates the development of metacognitive skills, which are crucial for students to manage and regulate their learning processes (Aisah & Nurjamin, 2021).

Reading Proficiency

Reading proficiency plays a critical role in academic success and future career development, serving as a key indicator of a student's ability to engage with complex academic materials. A strong foundation in reading is linked to higher academic achievement and cognitive development across various subjects. Studies consistently show a positive correlation between reading proficiency and overall academic performance (Cadiz-Gabejan & Quirino, 2021). Recent research continues to underscore the importance of reading proficiency as a significant predictor of educational success. McKenna et al. (2020) note that reading proficiency involves more than just decoding words—it requires comprehension, vocabulary knowledge, and critical thinking skills, all of which are essential for students to engage effectively with complex texts in various disciplines. Kirsch et al. (2020) further emphasize that low reading proficiency rates are detrimental to both educational attainment and economic opportunities, underscoring the broader implications of reading skills on students' futures.

Cognitive and linguistic skills are fundamental to reading proficiency, and these areas continue to be the focus of current research. Van den Broek et al. (2021) assert that working memory, phonemic awareness, and vocabulary play crucial roles in supporting text comprehension. These cognitive abilities are exceptionally vital for the effective processing and understanding of written material. Additionally, bilingual students face unique challenges and advantages in reading comprehension, influenced by their cognitive flexibility and language development. Kim et al. (2024) found that bilingual students often demonstrate enhanced reading comprehension skills in one language due to the cognitive benefits of switching between languages; however, challenges such as language transfer issues can complicate this process.

Methodology

Research Design

In this study, the researchers employed a quantitative design using the descriptive-correlational approach, as it allowed them to assess the association between variables without altering or influencing them. This method was beneficial in educational settings because, according to Fraenkel et al. (2019), it could provide insightful information about student outcomes without disrupting established instructional practices. Examples of these natural relationships included those between reading proficiency, instructional support, and verbal intelligence. The researcher identified patterns and trends in the data using descriptive-correlational analysis, providing a foundation for understanding how educational strategies align with students' reading proficiency levels. According to Gravetter and Wallnau (2016), this method not only helped identify potential predictors of reading proficiency but also assisted educators in recognizing impactful practices that could be emphasized to support student learning.

Respondents

The respondents of the study were SHS students who officially enrolled in Science, Technology, Engineering, and Mathematics (STEM), General Academic Strand (GAS), and Accountancy and Business Management (ABM) during the second semester of the academic year 2024-2025. The survey sample consisted of 100 respondents in total. This sample size was manageable for sample collection and allowed for sufficient data to be analyzed statistically (Creswell & Creswell, 2023). Hair et al. (2021) argue that a sample size of 100 or more participants was generally sufficient for detecting significant relationships among variables in correlational studies. This study employed a simple random sampling method, a probabilistic sampling method that ensures each member of the population has an equal chance of being selected, thereby reducing the threat of selection bias and increasing the generalizability of the findings (Saunders et al., 2019). A simple random method was a suitable choice for this study, as it enabled the selected respondents to represent the population of SHS students more reliably and validly (Taherdoost, 2016).

However, SHS students were chosen to become part of the study because of specific inclusion criteria: first, the students must be officially enrolled in the current semester. Second, these students must belong to the aforementioned strand. Third, these students must be in Grades 11 and 12 because Snow et al. (2002) emphasize that senior high school students face increasing academic demands that require strong reading comprehension skills, making them an ideal population for studying the effects of verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support on reading proficiency. Lastly, the selected locale was strategically chosen due to its easy accessibility for the researcher. This convenience greatly facilitated the smooth execution of the study, particularly in terms of data collection and coordination with participants. These criteria collectively justified their selection as suitable respondents.

Furthermore, exclusion criteria centered on the following: First, students who were not officially enrolled in the current semester were excluded from participation, as their academic engagement was not aligned with the context of the study. Second, if the student did not belong to the aforementioned strands, and lastly, if the student was under the influence of alcoholic drinks at the time of participation. These exclusion parameters were essential in maintaining the integrity and credibility of the study's findings; they may not have affected the researcher's answers.

Instrument

Three survey questionnaires were used to gather data from the study respondents. The first questionnaire was the Multiple Intelligence Profile Instrument VII by Tirri and Nokelainen (2011) and the Multiple Intelligences Inventory by McKenzie (1999). The second instrument was the Lecturers' Teaching Strategies in the Reading Classes, designed by Mohamed (2016). Lastly, the third instrument was the Reading Questionnaire adopted from Al-Qahtani (2016). To meet the research instrument's validity requirements, the researcher ensured the fidelity of the research tool through face validity. In this account, the survey questionnaires were forwarded to a panel of experts in questionnaire construction for a modification process to fit the culture of the respondents.

In this study, a four-point Likert scale was used because it is one of the most commonly used scales. To evaluate the level of each variable, the scales below were employed:

Procedure

At the outset, the researchers conceptualized the research framework. Upon approval, the adapted survey questionnaires were organized and submitted to a panel of examiners for face validation. Additionally, the researchers obtained permission from the Principal of the Senior High School Department to conduct the present study. Moreover, the researchers personally distributed the tool to the respondents and explained the rationale behind the research questions. Hereafter, the researchers retrieved the survey questionnaire after the respondents answered all the items indicated in the research tools. Afterward, the data were tabulated and subjected to statistical analysis. Henceforward, statistical results were analyzed meticulously and interpreted professionally to establish meaningful findings, conclusions, and recommendations.

Ethical Considerations

This study adhered to ethical standards in conducting educational research. Prior to data collection, approval was secured from the St.

John Paul II College of Davao's Thesis Committee. Permission was also obtained from the school principal to administer the survey among Senior High School students. Participation was voluntary, and respondents were informed of the study's purpose, assured of the confidentiality of their responses, and given the right to withdraw at any time without academic penalty. All data gathered were used solely for research purposes and reported in aggregate form to protect the anonymity of participants.

Results and Discussion

This section presents the data and findings of the study, based on the elicited responses of SHS students regarding verbal-linguistic intelligence, instructional support from the SHS Students' Perspective, and reading proficiency among SHS students.

Table 1. *Level of Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence of SHS Students*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Considering books important	3.37	0.720	Very High
2. Hearing words in head before reading, speaking, or writing down	3.33	0.620	Very High
3. Getting more out of listening to the radio or a spoken-word recording than from television or films	2.88	0.808	High
4. Enjoying word games like scrabble, anagrams, or password	2.99	0.870	High
5. Enjoying entertaining others with tongue twisters, nonsense rhymes, or puns	3.02	0.738	High
6. Enjoying reading books, magazines, and websites	3.06	0.722	High
7. Enjoying public speaking and participating in debates	2.59	0.933	High
8. Keeping and reading journals	2.75	0.757	High
9. Having written something recently that earned recognition or was a source of pride	2.82	0.730	High
10. Taking notes because it helps improve memory and understanding	3.49	0.611	Very High
11. Including frequent references in conversation	3.11	0.665	High
12. Being asked to explain the meaning of words used in writing and speaking	3.12	0.656	High
13. Contacting friends through letters or email	2.51	1.059	High
14. Having an interest in foreign languages	3.37	0.646	Very High
15. Finding it easy to learn languages like korean, english, or japanese	3.08	0.774	High
16. Finding english, social studies, and history easier in school than math and science	2.99	0.674	High
17. Finding word puzzles like crosswords or jumbles enjoyable	3.19	0.787	High
18. Finding writing a natural way to express ideas	3.29	0.624	Very High
19. Finding metaphors and vivid verbal expressions helpful for learning efficiently	3.12	0.729	High
20. Finding studies in the native language easy in school	3.23	0.694	High
Overall	3.07	0.360	High

The high rating of verbal-linguistic intelligence indicates that this variable is frequently observed, consistent with the findings of Rahmadina and Jufrizal (2021), who stated that verbal-linguistic intelligence is evident in students who are highly engaged in reading, writing, and using spoken language to convey ideas. These students are typically skilled at interpreting written and spoken content and can articulate thoughts clearly and effectively.

Similarly, De Jose (2019) emphasized that verbal proficiency is not only fundamental for academic success but also enhances students' ability to think critically and communicate persuasively. According to Anggraini and Lestari (2022), language-rich learning environments play a vital role in developing students' verbal-linguistic intelligence, which in turn supports better comprehension and performance in various subjects (Caloc & Baradillo, 2023).

In this variable, the line item with the highest mean rating was identified by the respondents, who took notes to help improve their memory and understanding. According to Arianto's study (2018), note-taking enhances students' concentration and helps them retain information more effectively during lectures or while studying.

Moreover, students who utilize note-taking strategies often demonstrate stronger reading comprehension and more organized thinking (Anggraini & Lestari, 2022). This suggests that taking notes is not only a mechanical process but also a cognitive one that supports deeper learning and memory retention. Furthermore, such practices reflect the students' metacognitive awareness and their ability to regulate their learning (Verbalplanet, 2024).

The item with the lowest mean, which is contacting friends through letters or email, is also described as high. In today's digital age, this result reflects a decline in students' preference for traditional modes of written communication. Safitri et al. (2022) explained that the rise of instant messaging apps and social media platforms has significantly altered the way young people interact, with faster and more informal communication being favored.

Verbalplanet (2024) also found that Generation Z learners often view email as more formal or professional and less suitable for everyday communication. Despite this, written communication remains an essential skill for academic and professional contexts, underscoring the importance of teaching students how to navigate both formal and informal communication modes.

Table 2. *Level of Instructional Support through the Lens of SHS Students*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Providing background information on the material before reading	3.33	0.697	Very High
2. Providing additional materials written in English outside of class	3.22	0.579	High
3. Asking to read the text aloud one by one in class	3.19	0.677	High
4. Asking a series of questions about a specific text to prepare for reading it	3.34	0.555	Very High
5. Teaching how to develop inference skills	3.17	0.726	High
6. Teaching how to skim a text to quickly grasp its general idea	3.39	0.665	Very High
7. Teaching how to scan a text to quickly locate specific information	3.41	0.621	Very High
8. Teaching how to summarize	3.64	0.523	Very High
9. Teaching how to analyze a text using critical thinking	3.53	0.611	Very High
10. Emphasizing learning language in all its forms —pronunciation, structure, etc.—in a reading course	3.43	0.555	Very High
11. Trying to make reading enjoyable	3.41	0.637	Very High
12. Giving the chance to select the topics of the reading texts	3.07	0.671	High
13. Encouraging the use of context clues to infer the meaning of unknown words	3.10	0.611	High
14. Applying English only policy in class	2.62	0.838	High
15. Arranging the class in groups or pairs to find the meaning of texts through discussion	3.12	0.729	High
16. Helping to explain the meaning of unfamiliar words	3.43	0.714	Very High
17. Allowing opportunities to guess what the text will be about before reading	3.26	0.691	Very High
18. Dividing the reading lesson into pre-reading, while-reading, and post-reading activities	3.05	0.770	High
19. Helping to link reading with meaningful communication	3.41	0.726	Very High
20. Pointing out reading problems	3.27	0.750	Very High
Overall	3.27	0.336	Very High

The very high rating of the respondents on instructional support indicates that this variable is consistently present. This aligns with the assertions of Alqurashi (2018), who emphasized that instructional support is critical in fostering student motivation and improving performance in blended learning environments. Effective instructional support encourages student engagement and ensures that learners feel guided and supported in their academic journey. Moreover, Zhang and Singh (2025) emphasized that instructional scaffolding enables students to develop critical reading strategies essential for comprehension and academic growth. The presence of strong instructional support also encourages metacognitive development, which is essential for students to manage and regulate their learning processes (Aisah & Nurjamin, 2021).

The very high level of instructional support of SHS students is due to the very high rating given by the respondents on teaching how to summarize. According to Reading Rockets (2025), teaching summarizing not only enhances students' comprehension skills but also enables them to identify main ideas and construct meaning from the text. Summarization is a key cognitive strategy that encourages active processing and retention of information. This finding is also supported by Wahyuningsih (2019), who found that students trained in summarizing strategies exhibited significantly improved academic reading outcomes and greater critical engagement with texts.

The item with the lowest mean, which is applying the English policy in class, is described as high. This supports the assertion of Bouguerra (2024), who found that an English-only policy in classrooms can create anxiety and reduce participation, particularly for learners who are not yet proficient. A more flexible approach that allows strategic use of the first language can enhance student comprehension and confidence. Additionally, García and Otheguy (2019) argued that embracing multilingual practices in the classroom helps create a more inclusive and learner-centered environment, especially in contexts where English is not the first language.

Table 3. *Level of Reading Proficiency of SHS Students*

<i>Item</i>	<i>Mean</i>	<i>Standard Deviation</i>	<i>Descriptive Equivalent</i>
1. Responding to questions about clearly stated details or facts in the text	3.36	0.523	Very High
2. Drawing inferences from information that is not explicitly stated	3.12	0.640	High
3. Understanding the implications of the passage	3.33	0.620	Very High
4. Determining the pronouns when reading the given text	3.28	0.587	Very High
5. Reading a text quickly and identifying the most important information	3.35	0.657	Very High
6. Using transitional phrases (e.g., first, then, however, moreover) to find specific information	3.33	0.637	Very High
7. Using keywords or phrases in the text to help answer a particular question	3.38	0.648	Very High
8. Identifying facts and opinions in the text	3.45	0.642	Very High
9. Recognizing the author's attitude and bias	3.41	0.605	Very High
10. Rearranging scrambled sentences or paragraphs	3.15	0.821	High
11. Recognizing the type of text to read (e.g., instructive, descriptive, informative)	3.20	0.586	High

12. Inferring a word's meaning by its position in a sentence (e.g., nouns, verbs, adjectives)	3.23	0.601	High
13. Using discourse markers (e.g., however, for example, in addition) to aid understanding	3.23	0.633	High
14. Skimming a text to grasp the main idea	3.36	0.659	Very High
15. Scanning the material before reading to gain a general understanding of the text	3.37	0.614	Very High
16. Analyzing contextual cues like synonyms, instances, and antonyms for unknown words	3.20	0.586	High
17. Identifying the purpose of sentences in the text (e.g., providing a definition, a description, an apology, or instructions)	3.22	0.613	High
18. Analyzing long sentences and phrases	3.42	0.572	Very High
19. Summarizing a text after reading it	3.50	0.595	Very High
20. Distinguishing main ideas from supporting details	3.49	0.595	Very High
Overall	3.32	0.341	Very High

The very high rating of the respondents on the study skills indicates that this variable is consistently present. This is aligned with the assertions of Hashemifardnia et al. (2021), who emphasized that reading proficiency is a core academic competency that fosters critical thinking, comprehension, and analytical abilities in students. Proficient reading not only enhances academic achievement but also supports students in lifelong learning and information processing (Masrai et al., 2021; Navarez et al., 2024).

In this variable, the item that has the highest mean rating given by the students is summarizing a text after reading it. This reflects the ability of students to condense information and identify key ideas—an essential component of reading comprehension. According to Ramirez-Avila and Barreiro (2021), summarization tasks help readers develop higher-order thinking skills and improve text retention and understanding. Similarly, Rahmadina and Jufriзал (2021) found that summarizing exercises enhance students' engagement and understanding of the text by encouraging them to organize and synthesize content meaningfully.

The item with the lowest mean rating makes inferences from information that is not explicitly stated and is described as high. This suggests that while students are capable readers, they may struggle with deeper comprehension tasks that require inference. As noted by Bayat and Çetinkaya (2020), inferencing is a sophisticated cognitive process that involves linking prior knowledge with textual clues, and it remains a challenge for many learners. Supporting this, Li and Gan (2022) argue that students require guided practice and strategic instruction to develop strong inferencing skills, which are essential for deeper text interpretation and analysis.

Table 4. Correlation Between Variables

Variables	Reading Proficiency		
	r-value	p-value	Decision on H0
Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	.569	.000	Rejected
Instructional Support	.638	.000	Rejected

Verbal-linguistic intelligence is related to reading proficiency, as evidenced by the rejection of the null hypothesis. The result was affirmed by the study of Sonia et al. (2021), who emphasized that verbal-linguistic intelligence contributes significantly to reading comprehension and textual analysis skills among high school students. Similarly, Rabago (2022) found that students with strong verbal-linguistic abilities tend to decode, understand, and interpret texts more effectively than their peers. This relationship is grounded in Gardner's Theory of Multiple Intelligences, which posits that verbal-linguistic intelligence enables individuals to utilize language to express themselves and comprehend others, making it crucial in the development of literacy. Therefore, students who excel in this intelligence domain are more likely to demonstrate advanced reading proficiency due to their linguistic aptitude.

Instructional support is also related to reading skills, as evidenced by the rejection of the null hypothesis. The result was affirmed by Domingo's (2025) study, which found that consistent instructional support, such as teacher scaffolding and targeted reading strategies, significantly enhances student performance in reading comprehension tasks. Likewise, Manansala and Jimenez (2020) emphasized that students are more likely to improve their reading skills when they receive constructive feedback, individualized attention, and guided reading interventions. This result is supported by Vygotsky's sociocultural theory, which emphasizes the role of social interactions and instructional guidance in the cognitive development of learners. With appropriate support from teachers, students can bridge learning gaps, develop independent reading strategies, and ultimately perform better in reading assessments.

Table 5. Influence of Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence and Instructional Support on the Reading Proficiency of SHS Students

Variables	Reading Proficiency				
	βCoefficient	F-value	R2	t-value	p-value
Verbal-Linguistic Intelligence	.308	45.557	.474	3.806	.000
Instructional Support	.477			5.501	.000

Verbal-linguistic intelligence influences the reading proficiency of SHS students because it enhances their awareness of the meanings of words, the structures of texts, and the contexts of texts, and these things are essential for understanding and analyzing texts in line

with the concept of Information Processing Theory (Atkinson & Shiffrin, 1968), where learning involves encoding, storing, and retrieving information. Verbal-linguistic intelligence enhances the ability to process language-based information, enabling students to retain vocabulary, understand syntax, and apply linguistic knowledge effectively during reading. Setyaningsih et al. (2022) affirmed that verbal-linguistic intelligence supports mastery of reading, writing, speaking, and listening—key language processing tasks. Similarly, Mujiono et al. (2023) emphasized that strong verbal-linguistic ability improves academic performance in reading-based subjects. These findings suggest that verbal-linguistic intelligence equips learners with essential skills for academic reading, thereby facilitating deeper engagement with and understanding of written material.

Instructional support also influences the reading proficiency of SHS students because it provides scaffolded guidance, feedback, and learning strategies that will help students develop productive habits for understanding, organizing, and retaining academic content in accordance with the concept of Bruner's Constructivist Learning Theory, which asserts that learners build new knowledge through active involvement and support from educators. Hamre and Downer (2021) highlighted that instructional support helps learners engage more deeply with reading materials. Additionally, Pianta et al. (2020) emphasized the impact of teacher guidance and feedback on student learning outcomes in literacy. These findings suggest that when students receive meaningful instructional support, they are better equipped to navigate complex texts, develop effective critical reading strategies, and enhance their overall reading proficiency.

Conclusions

The aforementioned results and findings of the study served as the baseline for the formulation of the following conclusions: The level of verbal-linguistic intelligence among SHS students is high. It means that verbal-linguistic intelligence is frequently manifested. Moreover, the level of instructional support is very high. This means that instructional support is always manifested. Additionally, the reading proficiency level of SHS students has reached a descriptive level, which is very high. Thus, it is also always manifested. In general, verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support have a significant relationship with students' reading proficiency. Furthermore, the regression analysis revealed that these two factors collectively account for 47.4% of the variation in reading proficiency, confirming their substantial influence.

Based on the findings and conclusions, the following recommendations were crafted for consideration by the beneficiaries of this study:

To elevate the high level of verbal-linguistic intelligence, the researcher recommends that the SHS faculty, particularly the English teachers, provide students with opportunities to practice composing both digital and traditional (written or printed) letters. Furthermore, the IT department may also be encouraged to promote the proper use of digital communication channels. For example, instead of posting announcements on social media platforms such as Facebook, they may consider sending individual emails to the concerned recipients or using group emails to reach all relevant individuals.

To sustain the very high level of instructional support, the researcher suggests that SHS teachers may expose students to various speaking activities such as role-playing, talk shows, and storytelling. These activities offer students opportunities to practice and improve their English-speaking skills in an engaging and interactive way.

To sustain the very high level of reading proficiency, the researcher recommends that SHS teachers conduct weekly guided reading sessions that incorporate the use of context clues, such as idiomatic expressions. This approach may help enhance students' understanding of implicature and support a deeper comprehension of implied meanings in texts.

Since verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support are related to the reading proficiency of SHS students, SHS teachers may integrate both oral and written exercises within their teaching. By employing methods such as vocabulary-building activities and promoting active listening in discussions, students can enhance both their verbal and reading skills simultaneously.

The significant influence of verbal-linguistic intelligence and instructional support on reading proficiency suggests that integrating professional development programs focused on strategies that enhance students' verbal-linguistic intelligence is beneficial. Providing support and resources for teachers can lead to more effective learning environments and improved reading capabilities, ultimately improving academic performance and literacy outcomes.

The present study used a quantitative research design employing a descriptive-correlational approach with two independent variables and one dependent variable. For future researchers, an experimental study may be conducted in which students are observed while reading. This could involve a "close reading" approach, and the researcher uses a checklist to note the words that students mispronounce and those they have difficulty understanding. This method may offer deeper insights into students' reading challenges and help identify areas for targeted improvement.

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